

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 7

Axiomatic Design

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Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. Definition of Axiomatic Design
2. Axiomatic Design Application
3. How to do an Axiomatic Design

7.0 Introduction

This seventh week's topics responds to the fourth course objective states, "Develop a conceptual design with material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability". To create a design concept the axiomatic design is used as a methodology.

The sixth-week topic aims to help the engineering designer to grasp the ability to search for information and use it to identify the gaps and create a new idea.

The fifth-week topics correspond to the fourth-course objectives, which state, "Develop a conceptual design with the material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability".

The fourth week's topics respond to the first-course objective, "To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process".

The third week's topics discuss communication, collaboration and team success, even in a diverse team membership or multi-disciplinary nature.

The second week's response to the second-course objective states, "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication". It also

In the first week's discussion, the challenge to take part in the Sustainable Development Goals action using the Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) that served as a theme to the Engineering Design Challenge 2022, was taken on board as an engineering design team is discussed and organised in the second week.

7.1. Definition of Axiomatic Design

Design methods leads a design engineer to one or more good solutions to a design problem. Axiomatic Design was developed by Nam P. Suh, a mechanical engineering professor at MIT. Suh's intention was to identify a set of fundamental laws or principles for engineering design and use them as the basis for a rigorous theory of design. A basis for design is focused around two design axioms (MIT):

Axiom 1. The independence axiom:

Maintain the independence of the functional requirements

An optimal design always maintains the independence of the functional requirements of the design.

Axiom 2. The information axiom:

Minimize the information content of the design

In an acceptable design the design parameters (DPs) and functional requirements (FRs) are related in such a way that a specific DP can be adjusted to satisfy its corresponding FR without affecting other functional requirements. Axiom 2 is considered as a second rule for selecting designs. If there is more than one design alternative that meets Axiom 1 and has equivalent performance, then the design with the lesser amount of information should be selected.

Axiomatic Design is useful in focusing the designer or design team on the core functionality required in a new product. The method provides tools for classifying existing designs once they are represented in the key design equation that uses the design matrix to relate functional requirements to design parameters. Axiomatic Design is also one of the most widely recognized design methodologies, especially within the academic community (where it originated - MIT).

Axiomatic design enhances creativity by eliminating bad ideas early and designers. It helps the design decision making process in:

- Correcting decisions
- Shortening lead time
- Improving the quality of products
- Dealing with complex systems
- Simplifying service and maintenance
- Enhancing creativity

7.2 Axiomatic Design Application

Axiomatic design is a systems design methodology using matrix methods to systematically analyze the transformation of customer needs into functional requirements, design parameters, and process variables (Axiomatic Design). The Axiomatic Design procedure is a mapping of one set of variables to another by examining the customer's needs and expressing them as a list of attributes - the mapping of customer needs into functional requirements to be a prerequisite step that takes place prior to the generation of feasible concepts.

Figure 23. Nam Suh's design Axiomatic Design pprocess.

Consumer Attributes:

Consumer attributes (CAs) are characteristics, properties and behaviours that describe a consumer needs. CAs are characteristics that are defined by the customer space (MIT).

Functional Requirement:

Functional requirements (FRs) are a minimum set of independent requirements that completely characterizes the functional needs of the product (or software, organizations, systems, etc.) in the functional domain. By definition, each FR is independent of every other FR at the time the FRs are established (MIT).

✓ *Constraint:*

Constraints (Cs) are bounds on acceptable solutions. There are two kinds of constraints: input constraints and system constraints. Input constraints are imposed as part of the design specifications. System constraints are constraints imposed by the system in which the design solution must function (MIT).

Design Parameters:

Design parameters (DPs) are the key physical (or other equivalent terms in the case of software design, etc.) variables in the physical domain that characterize the design that satisfies the specified FRs (MIT).

Process variable:

Process variables (PVs) are the key variables (or other equivalent term in the case of software design, etc.) in the process domain that characterizes the process that can generate the specified DPs (MIT).

7.2.1 Axiomatic Design Examples

Developing a Model Prototype Rainwater Harvesting Infrastructure, RHI (Betasolo & Smith)

Figure 24. The Rainwater Harvesting Infrastructure Prototype Adapted from (Betasolo & Smith)

The figure shows a model of a rainwater harvesting infrastructure of which an axiomatic design was used in the creating of a model. The 4 Axiomatic Design (AD) domains are applied and it is shown in the next figure.

Fig.6a. AD mapping from CN to FR, to PD and to PV. Adapted from [7].

Figure 25. The Axiomatic Design Diagram for the RHI (Rainwater Harvesting Infrastructure) Adapted from (Betasolo & Smith)

The mapping of the 2 domains (Functional Requirements and Design Parameters) to design the model rainwater harvesting infrastructure prototype is shown in the next figure.

		DPs	RHI System	Weight less & transparent	coefficient of runoff, e	dimension of catchment	shower or rain	filter membrane	tank	chlorination	outlet
FRs		DP0	DP1	DP1.1	DP2	DP2.1	DP3	DP4	DP5	DP6	
FRO	Fabricate an RHI model prototype	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
FR1	Determine the material to be used		x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
FR1.1	Determine reliability of collecting surface		0	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	
FR2	Estimate rainwater to be harvested		0	0	x	0	0	0	0	0	
FR2.1	Simulate rain (dry & wet)		0	0	0	x	0	0	0	0	
FR3	Remove dirt and other contaminants		0	0	0	0	x	0	0	0	
FR4	Contain water		0	0	0	0	0	x	0	0	
FR5	Protect water quality		0	0	0	0	0	0	x	0	
FR6	Provide point for distribution		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	x	

Figure 26. The Axiomatic Design Matrix for the RHI (Rainwater Harvesting Infrastructure) Adapted from (Betasolo & Smith)

Above photo: rainfall simulated from rain tray falling above the catchment

Photo below: rainfall captured outside

Figure 27. The Axiomatic Design Simulation for the RHI Adapted from (Betasolo & Smith)

7.3. How to do an Axiomatic Design

The ultimate goal of Axiomatic Design is to establish a science base for design and to improve design activities by providing the designer with a theoretical foundation based on logical and rational thought processes and tool.

Step 1: Answer the following questions:

1. What we want to achieve?
2. How we want to achieve it?

Step 2: Follow and use the Design Framework below

Axiomatic Design Framework The Concept of Domains

Four Domains of the Design World.
The {x} are characteristic vectors of each domain.

Figure by MIT OCW. After Figure 1.2 in [Suh 2001].

Figure 28. The Axiomatic Design Framework, Concept of Domain Adapted from (MIT)

Characteristics of the four domains of the design world

Domains Character Vectors	Customer Domain {CAs}	Functional Domain {FRs}	Physical Domain {DPs}	Process Domain {PVs}
Manufacturing	Attributes which consumers desire	Functional requirements specified for the product	Physical variables which can satisfy the functional requirements	Process variables that can control design parameters (DPs)
Materials	Desired performance	Required Properties	Micro-structure	Processes
Software	Attributes desired in the software	Output Spec of Program codes	Input Variables or Algorithms Modules Program codes	Sub-routines machine codes compilers modules
Organization	Customer satisfaction	Functions of the organization	Programs or Offices or Activities	People and other resources that can support the programs
Systems	Attribute desired of the overall system	Functional requirements of the system	Machines or components, sub-components	Resources (human, financial, materials, etc.)
Business	ROI	Business goals	Business structure	Human and financial resource

Table by MIT OCW. After Table 1.1 in [Suh 2001].

Figure 29. The Domain Characteristics Adapted from (MIT)

References

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